

DepIn-O: Validation

¹Appendix to “DepIn-O: an Ontology on Dependency Injection Software Frameworks”

This appendix presents DepIn-O’s validation, performed by mapping DepIn-O’s **Catalog of Concepts** to instances for each framework analyzed.

1. Language: Java

1.1. Framework: Spring

Listing 1. Consumer with Constructor Injector

```
1 @Component
2 public class ConsumerCI {
3     DependencyA dep;
4
5     public ConsumerCI(DependencyA da) { // constructor injector
6         dep = da;
7     }
8 }
```

Listing 2. Consumer with Method Injector

```
1 @Component
2 public class ConsumerMI {
3     public void generalMethod(DependencyA da) {} // method injector
4 }
```

Listing 3. Consumer with Property Injector

```
1 @Component
2 public class ConsumerPI {
3     @Autowired DependencyA dep; // property injector
4 }
```

Listing 4. Abstract Dependency

```
1 public interface DependencyA {}
```

Listing 5. Primary Dependency

```
1 @Component @Primary
2 public class DepImpl implements DependencyA {}
```

Listing 6. Qualified Dependency

```
1 @Component @Qualifier("Alt")
2 public class DepImpl2 implements DependencyA {}
```

Listing 7. Dependency Specification (in a Property Injector)

```
1 @Autowired @Qualifier("Alt") DependencyA dep ;
```

Listing 8. Decorator (as Primary Dependency and Consumer of a Qualified Dependency)

```
1 @Component @Primary
2 public class DecoratorA implements DependencyA {
3     @Autowired @Qualifier("Alt") DependencyA dep ;
4 }
```

Listing 9. Singleton Dependency

```
1 @Component @Scope("singleton")
2 public class DepSing {}
3 // this is the default scope in Spring
```

Listing 10. Dependent Dependency

```
1 @Component @Scope("prototype")
2 public class DepProto {}
```

Listing 11. Request Scoped Dependency

```
1 @Component @RequestScope
2 public class DepReq {}
```

Listing 12. Session Scoped Dependency

```
1 @Component @SessionScope
2 public class DepSes {}
```

Listing 13. Application Scoped Dependency

```
1 @Component @ApplicationScope
2 public class DepApp {}
```

1.2. Framework: CDI

Listing 14. Consumer with Constructor Injector

```
1 public class ConsumerCI {
2     DependencyA dep ;
3
4     @Inject
5     public ConsumerCI(DependencyA da) { // constructor injector
6         dep = da ;
7     }
8 }
```

Listing 15. Consumer with Method Injector

```
1 public class ConsumerMI{
2     public void generalMethod(DependencyA da) {} // method injector
3 }
```

Listing 16. Consumer with Property Injector

```
1 public class ConsumerPI {
2     @Inject DependencyA dep ;
3 }
```

Listing 17. Abstract Dependency

```
1 public interface DependencyA {}
```

Listing 18. Primary Dependency

```
1 @Default
2 public class DepImpl implements DependencyA {}
3
4 @Alternative
5 public class DepImpl2 implements DependencyA {}
6
7 // The annotation @Default is optional. There must be only one class not annotated as @Alternative
   that will be the Primary Dependency.
```

Listing 19. Qualified Dependency

```
1 Qualified Dependency
2 @Named("Impl1")
3 public class DepImpl implements DependencyA {}
4
5 @Named("Impl2")
6 public class DepImpl2 implements DependencyA {}
7
8 // Using the annotation @Named requires all dependencies to be qualified.
```

Listing 20. Dependency Specification (in a Property Injector)

```
1 @Inject @Named("Impl2") DependencyA dep ;
```

Listing 21. Decorator

```
1 @Decorator
2 public class DecoratorA implements DependencyA {
3     @Inject @Delegate DependencyA dep ;
4 }
5 // delegates dep to be resolved by the dependency implementation that had been previously defined as
   // default/primary
6
7 // beans.xml
8     <decorators >
9         <class >{ packagepath }.DecoratorA </class >
10    </decorators >
```

Listing 22. Singleton Dependency

```
1 @Singleton
2 public class DepSing {}
```

Listing 23. Dependent Dependency

```
1 @Dependent
2 public class DepDepend {}
3 // this is the default scope in CDI
```

Listing 24. Request Scoped Dependency

```
1 @RequestScoped
2 public class DepReq {}
```

Listing 25. Session Scoped Dependency

```
1 @SessionScoped
2 public class DepSes {}
```

Listing 26. Application Scoped Dependency

```
1 @ApplicationScoped
2 public class DepApp {}
```

2. Language: Python

2.1. Framework: Dependency Injector

Listing 27. Consumer with Constructor Injector

```
1 class ConsumerCI:
2     def __init__(self, service : DependencyA):
3         self.dependency = service
```

Listing 28. Consumer with Method Injector

```
1 class ConsumerMI:
2     def test(self, service : DependencyA):
```

Consumer (with Property Injector): not possible to implement in Python/Dependency Injector.

Listing 29. Abstract Dependency

```
1 class DependencyA(metaclass=abc.ABCMeta):
```

Listing 30. Dependency Implementations

```
1 Dependency Implementations
2 class DepImpl1(DependencyA):
3
4 class DepImpl2(DependencyA):
```

Listing 31. Decorator

```
1 class DecoratorA(DependencyA):      #decorator
2     def __init__(self, service):
3         self.dep = service
```

Listing 32. Dependency Injection (in the Container)

```
1 class Container(containers.DeclarativeContainer):
2     dep = providers.Factory(DependencyA)
3     deco = providers.Factory(DecoratorA, dep)
4     con = providers.Factory(ConsumerCI, deco)
```

Listing 33. Dependency Specification (in the Container)

```
1 container = Container()
2 container.dep.override(providers.Factory(Deplmpl1))
```

Primary Dependency & Qualified Dependency: Since Dependency Specification is always required (either the concrete dependency is directly provided or *AbstractFactory* must be overridden by providing the concrete dependency), all Dependency Implementations fit our Qualified Dependency definition, and none of them fit our Primary Dependency definition.

Listing 34. Singleton Dependency

```
1 class Container(containers.DeclarativeContainer):
2     depSing = providers.Singleton(Deplmpl1)
```

Listing 35. Dependent Dependency

```
1 class Container(containers.DeclarativeContainer):
2     depDependent = providers.Factory(Deplmpl1)      #Factory = Dependent scope
```

Listing 36. Request Scoped Dependency

```
1 #resets Container/Dependencies with every new request
2
3 class GetReq(BaseHTTPRequestHandler):
4     # code
5
6 class WebServer(HTTServer):
7     def service_actions(self):
8         # if GetReq signals a new request then
9         self.dependency = Container().dep()
```

Session Scoped Dependency: reset Container/Dependencies with every new Session, using cookies. Depends on integration with another framework to be implemented.

Application Scoped Dependency: never reset the Container/Dependencies.

3. Language: C#

3.1. Framework: Autofac

The container builder is imperative to support many of the concepts' instantiation, so we start showing how it is created and prepared for usage first.

Listing 37. Container set up

```
1 var builder = new ContainerBuilder();
2 // code
3 var container = builder.Build();
```

Listing 38. Consumer with Constructor Injector

```
1 public class ConsumerCI{
2     IDependencyA dep ;
3
4     public ConsumerCI(IDependencyA service){
5         dep = service ;
6     }
7 }
```

Listing 39. Consumer with Method Injector

```
1 public class ConsumerMI{
2     public void test(IDependencyA dep){}
3 }
```

Listing 40. Consumer with Property Injector

```
1 public class ConsumerPI{
2     public required IDependencyA dep { get; init; }
3 }
```

Listing 41. Abstract Dependency

```
1 public interface DependencyA {}
```

Listing 42. Dependency Implementations

```
1 public class DepImpl1 : IDependencyA {}
2
3 public class DepImpl2 : IDependencyA {}
```

Listing 43. Primary Dependency

```
1 builder.RegisterType<DepImpl1>().As<IDependencyA>(); // sets up DepImpl1 as the Primary Dependency
2 builder.RegisterType<ConsumerCI>().PropertiesAutowired(); // automatically sets up the injection of
   the primary dependency into the consumer
```

Listing 44. Qualified Dependency

```
1 builder.RegisterType<DepImpl2>().Keyed<IDependencyA>("Impl2");
```

Listing 45. Dependency Specification via Constructor Injector

```
1 public ConsumerCI([ KeyFilter("Impl2")] IDependencyA service){ // Key in Constructor Method
2     dep = service ;
3 }
4
5 // at the container builder
6 builder.RegisterType<ConsumerCI>().WithAttributeFiltering(); // specifies to look at the filters
   to know which dependency is to be injected
```

Listing 46. Decorator

```
1 public class DecoratorA : IDependencyA{
2     IDependencyA dep ;
3
4     public DecoratorA(IDependencyA service){
5         dep = service ;
6     }
7 }
8
9 // at the container builder
10 builder.RegisterDecorator<DecoratorA , IDependencyA>();
```

Listing 47. Singleton Dependency

```
1 builder.RegisterType<DepImpl1>().As<IDependencyA>().SingleInstance();
```

Listing 48. Dependent Dependency

```
1 builder.RegisterType<DepImpl1>().As<IDependencyA>().InstancePerDependency();
2 // this is the default scope in Autofac
```

Listing 49. Request Scoped Dependency

```
1 builder . RegisterType <DepImpl1 >() . As <IDependencyA >() . InstancePerRequest ();
```

Session Scoped Dependency: According to Autofac’s documentation, “This road is fraught with peril and is totally unsupported¹.”

Application Scoped Dependency: declared like the Singleton scope, but in the root container of the application.

3.2. Framework: Simple Injector

The container is imperative to support many of the concepts’ instantiation, so we start showing how it is created; when the first call to *GetInstance*, *GetAllInstances* or *Verify* is made, the container locks itself to prevent any future changes being made by explicit registrations.

Listing 50. Container set up

```
1 var container = new Container();
2 // code
3 container . Verify (); // Verify the container 's configuration , also locks it .
```

Listing 51. Consumer with Constructor Injector

```
1 public class ConsumerCI{
2     IDependencyA dep ;
3
4     public ConsumerCI(IDependencyA service){ // constructor injector
5         dep = service ;
6     }
7 }
8
9 // at the container
10 container . Register <ConsumerCI >(); // container registration
```

Listing 52. Consumer with Method Injector

```
1 public class ConsumerMI{
2     public void test(IDependencyA dep){}
3 }
```

Listing 53. Consumer with Property Injector

```
1 public class ConsumerPI{
2     [Import] public IDependencyA dep { get; set; }
3 }
4
5 // additional set-up necessary for property injection to work
6 class ImportPropertySelectionBehavior : IPropertySelectionBehavior
7 {
8     public bool SelectProperty(Type implementationType , PropertyInfo prop) =>
9         prop . GetCustomAttributes ( typeof ( ImportAttribute ) ) . Any ();
10 }
11
12 // at the container
13 container . Options . PropertySelectionBehavior = new ImportPropertySelectionBehavior (); // enabling
14 // property injection
15 container . Register <ConsumerPI >(); // container registration
```

Listing 54. Abstract Dependency

```
1 public interface DependencyA {}
```

Listing 55. Dependency Implementations

```
1 public class DepImpl1 : IDependencyA {}
2 public class DepImpl2 : IDependencyA {}
```

¹<https://autofac.readthedocs.io/en/latest/faq/instance-per-session.html>

```

3
4 // registering them in the container
5 container.Collection.Append<IDependencyA, DepImpl1>();
6 container.Collection.Append<IDependencyA, DepImpl2>();

```

Listing 56. Primary Dependency

```

1 container.Register<IDependencyA, DepImplDef>();

```

Qualified Dependency: According to Simple Injector’s documentation: “Resolving instances by a key is a feature that is deliberately left out of Simple Injector, because it invariably leads to a design where the application tends to have numerous dependencies on the DI container itself. To resolve a keyed instance you will likely need to call directly into the Container instance and this leads to the Service Locator anti-pattern².”

Listing 57. Decorator

```

1 public class DecoratorA : IDependencyA{
2     IDependencyA dep ;
3
4     public DecoratorA(IDependencyA service){
5         dep = service ;
6     }
7 }
8
9 // at the container
10 container.RegisterDecorator<IDependencyA, DecoratorA>();

```

Listing 58. Singleton Dependency

```

1 container.Register<IDependencyA, DepImplDef>(Lifestyle.Singleton) ;

```

Listing 59. Dependent Dependency

```

1 container.Register<IDependencyA, DepImplDef>(Lifestyle.Transient) ;
2 // this is the default scope in Simple Injector

```

Listing 60. Request Scoped Dependency

```

1 container.Options.DefaultScopedLifestyle = new WebRequestLifestyle();
2 container.Register<IDependencyA, DepImplDef>(Lifestyle.Scoped);

```

Session Scoped Dependency: According to Simple Injector’s documentation, “This lifestyle is deliberately left out of Simple Injector (...) instead of using Per HTTP Session lifestyle, you will usually be better off by writing a stateless service that can be registered as singleton and let it communicate with the ASP.NET Session cache to handle cached user-specific data.” <<https://docs.simpleinjector.org/en/latest/lifetimes.html>>

Listing 61. Application Scoped Dependency

```

1 container.Options.DefaultScopedLifestyle = new WcfOperationLifestyle();
2 container.Register<IUserRepository, SqlUserRepository>(Lifestyle.Scoped);

```

²<https://docs.simpleinjector.org/en/latest/howto.html>